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THE EFFICIENCY OF THE WELLNESS TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON THE SOUTH KOREA'S EXAMPLE

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ABSTRACT

The most favourable solution for improving tourists visiting flow in Uzbekistan, both locals and foreigners, is enhancing the popularity of the wellness tourism. And, of course we need a perfect example for that, meaningly we can take one certain country which is already great in the wellness branch of the tourism field. In our case, it is the South Korea. Based on the research that has been done, it is known that South Korea mostly offers stress revealing activities which are seen in their unique spa centers, special cafes and nature made destinations. Uzbekistan is also developing in this field with its picturesque spots which do not allow any tourist to pass them by. Uzbekistan needs to improve all the possible facilities that it already has and make these destinations more popular. We should not focus only on the beauty of the nature made destinations but also make a great benefit and profit of them in order to improve the tourism field in Uzbekistan.

Key words: wellness tourism, healthcare, Korean spas (jjimhijilbang, 찜질방), Chingan, Charvak, "Zaamin", "Amirsoy", Jeju island, Bukhasan National Park of Seoul, Yeosu, rural tourism, "Haliu" (Korean wave).

O'ZBEKISTONDA SALOMATLIK TURIZMINING JANUBIY KOREYA O'RNAGI ASOSDA SAMARADORLIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Sog'lomlashtirish turizim mashhurligini oshirish O'zbekistonda mahalliy va xorijiy sayyohlar oqimini rivojlantirish uchun eng yaxshi qarordir. Va, albatta, buning

uchun bizga a'lo darajali namuna kerak, ya'ni biz aniq bir mamlakatni, qaysiki allaqachon bu sohada o'zini namoyon qila olganligini ko'rsatishimiz lozim bo'ladi. Bizning holatimizda, bu Janubiy Koreya mamlakati hisoblanadi. Izlanishlar natijasida, ma'lumki Janubiy Koreya asosan stressni bartaraf qiladigan omillarni amalga oshirgan. Bu ularning noodatiy spa maskanlari, maxsus kafelari va tabiat yaratgan manzaralarida ifodalangan. O'zbekiston ham bu borada o'zining ko'rkam maskanlari bilan taraqqiyot sari bormoqda va hech bir sayyoh shu joylardan befarq o'tolmaydi. Kelajakda O'zbekiston yuqorida bayon qilingan joylarni yanada mashhur bo'lishi uchun barcha imkoniyatlarni rivojlantirishi lozim. Biz faqatgina tabiat yaratgan go'zalliklar bilan chegaralanib qolmasdan, ulardan unumli foydalanib, O'zbekistonda turizm sohasini yanada ko'klarga ko'tarishimiz kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: sog'lomlashtirish turizimi, sog'liqni saqlash, Koreya spa maskanlari (jjimhijilbang, 찜질방), Chimyon, Chorvoq, "Zomin", "Amirsoy", Jeju qirgogi, Buhasan Seul milliy parki, Yosu, chekka turizim, "Haliu" (Koreya to'lqin).

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ НА ПРИМЕРЕ ЮЖНОЙ КОРЕИ

АБСТРАКТ

Самым подходящим решением для улучшения потока туристов в Узбекистан, как местных, так и иностранных, является повышение популярности оздоровительного туризма. И, конечно же, нам нужен отличный пример для этого, то есть мы можем взять одну определенную страну, которая уже является превосходной в сфере оздоровительного туризма. В нашем случае – это Южная Корея. Основываясь на исследовании, которое было проведено, известно, что Южная Корея, в основном, предоставляет деятельности, которые помогают избавиться от стресса, рассмотренные в их необычных спа-центрах, специальных тематических кафе и местах, сделанные

природой. Узбекистан также развивается в этой сфере, представляя свои красивые места, которые не позволят ни одному туристу пройти мимо. Узбекистан нуждается в улучшении всех существующих возможностей, которые уже у него есть и сделать те места более популярными. Мы не должны фокусироваться только на красоте мест, сделанные природой, но, также извлечь пользу и прибыль от них, чтобы улучшить сферу туризма в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: оздоровительный туризм, здравоохранение, корейские спа (Чимчильбан, 찜질방), Чимган, Чарвак, “Заамин”, “Амирсой”, остров Джеджу, Национальный парк Сеула Бухасан, Ёсу, сельский туризм, “Халию” (корейская волна).

Introduction. For the past years, Uzbekistan has been attracting tourists and even scientists only for the historical destinations which are full of mysterious monuments, architecture, etc. Even among locals domestic tourism started a bit decreasing due to the fact that citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan want to experience something new and unique and not always visiting the sights which are all similar in terms of architecture, structure of the buildings and so forth. It is a known fact that pilgrimage or more commonly known as ziyarah tourism has been involving locals to travel to different cities and regions. Most popular among them are Bukhara and Samarkand. These two cities are very well known among foreigners as well. But there is a question again, for what? Not surprisingly, for the historical sites too. So, this is the issue we, future specialists in the tourism field, should deal with and offer modern solutions to attract not only tourists from various countries but also locals as well. In this article a reader can find the most preferable solutions to enhance the level of the wellness tourism in Uzbekistan. The most emphasized solution will be on the stress-revealing activities which would be offered and presented in popular nature made destinations in sunny country, Uzbekistan. While reading the article it can be understood that those

activities are provided only in South Korea, the country which is taken as a role model for improving the wellness tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The aim of this article is to promote stress-revealing activities in targeted country. Before the explanation of this solution the clear definition of the “wellness tourism” ideology is given below in order to make sure that those possible solutions would be really helpful.

The concept of the wellness tourism. Health or more known as a wellness tourism is the travel to certain places for the purpose of prevention and promotion of health. The competitiveness of the tourism industry affects the success of destinations. In fact, it has proven to be an essential requirement for the long-term growth of a local or national tourism industry in a highly competitive market. Tourist destinations are no longer special and unique natural, cultural, artistic and ecological resources, but attractive products that offer attentive services to provide travelers with unforgettable vacations (Rodríguez López, 2022). In every sphere, especially in the tourism industry, the service plays a significant role. What makes tourists come back to certain country, city, destination? It is definitely service. In the topic we are dealing with all employees should provide a great customer service while accepting guests in different healthcare spots. The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) defines wellness tourism as: Health tourism is a type of tourism activity that aims to improve and balance all major areas of human life, including the physical, mental, emotional, professional, intellectual and spiritual realms. The main motivations of wellness tourists are to engage in preventative, active and lifestyle enhancing activities such as fitness, healthy eating, relaxation, body care and healing treatments (Rodríguez-López, 2022). People can get distracted in a good way by doing things like practicing yoga, eating healthy, getting massages and spa treatments, and exercising. These activities are also known as ways to prevent problems before they happen, make good choices before something goes wrong, and improve lifestyle. If people visit places that are focused on health while they travel, they can have a good balance of feeling good in their body and emotions, which helps keep them healthy. There are several components which are

included in the wellness tourism. They are natural environment, spirituality, sports and events (Emerald, 2021).

The most favorable solutions in stress-revealing activities for Uzbekistan based on the examples of South Korea. First of all, we should understand why the tourism sphere has increased so much in the South Korea before talking about the examples. It has been a pretty while since the word “Haliu” (한류) or also known as the “Korean wave” started to gain popularity all over the world and attract tourists. “Haliu” stands for Korean culture, mostly such as korean dramas, movies, famous korean pop music (k-pop) and korean fashion (Zidehsaraei, 2015). The fans of those dramas or k-pop love to visit special sights devoted to these themes. There is even an open-air museum or just an amazing park with the statues of the actors from the famous korean drama “Winter Sonata” in the Namisom island, South Korea. It is really gorgeous if you visit this wonderful place especially in the seasons of autumn and winter. While walking in that park a person can dive into the romantic atmosphere and forget about all problems.

And what about the examples which are going to be taken for Uzbekistan? Actually, there are dozens of special destinations which indeed help people escape from the hustle and bustle of the city life. The first is anti-stress cafes with the animals (which can be seen on the figure 1).

Figure 1: Anti-stress animal café in Seoul

Source: Korean go go, 2022

The most popular district with this kind of cafes is Myeongdong, Seoul. You can find almost any animal beginning with the cats ending with baby kangaroos. Koreans are known as the workaholics and when they visit those cafes, they say that it is really

helpful for them to avoid stress and just relax. Many scientists also proved that playing with the animals helps to be more energetic and increases the hormone of happiness, serotonin. Such type of cafes is located only in South Korea in the whole world for now. So, it would be great to create such animal cafes in Uzbekistan as well. It would increase the domestic tourism firstly. People would start traveling inside the cities. And then it would be very unique for foreign visitors too. Uzbekistan is famous mostly for the cheap travel. So, rather than going to South Korea which can require a really good budget tourists can just come to Uzbekistan and experience the same but with more affordable budget. Another positive side of those cafes is the protection of animals. It is not a secret that many animals can suffer on the streets because there might not always be shelters for them. But in those cafes, all those animals would be taken care and protected.

Unusual spa centers

Another example for relaxation is creating special spa centers like jjimjilbangs (찜질방). Koreans' attitude towards spa centers is totally in a different way than in any other countries. They allot special places and lands to construct spa centers (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Traditional spa centers in South Korea and special uniform to wear there

Source: Living + Nomads, 2023

People are also given special clothes such as hats (which are actually towel) and t-shirts with shorts. They can even spend their whole day there. This place is especially popular among young generation. People are also treated with the delicious meals from the Korean cuisine there. These spa centers are multifunctional that even some special game zones are available, comfortable tables and chairs are also placed there for having a lunch, dinner. Briefly speaking, tourists can not only enjoy the spa itself but also do other activities as well. The most famous spa centers are “Banyan Tree Spa”, “Centum Spa Land”, “The Ananti Cove-Water House” (Korea Tourism Organization, 2020). About 13-15 jjimjilbangs are located in each of them where people are given special treatments.

Considering rural tourism as the chance to enhance the domestic tourism’s level. As a matter of fact, most of the spots devoted to the well-being of a human are located in suburbs of the city, rural tourism is becoming really important. In many European countries the rural tourism is considered to be the most essential type. And mostly tourists love to experience "wine tourism" (Corina, 2018). But, here, in Uzbekistan it would be better to focus more on the stress escaping activities which could enhance the spiritual energy. It means that creating more spa centres which are only specialized in offering a very pleasant relaxation (not just like in most hotels) would be the best choice. They have special buildings and places obtained by spas. We should also take it into account. Moreover, if those spas are located in some rural areas with the fresh air, it would be like a double pleasant touristic experience because of the proximity to the nature. A tourist can fully enjoy all spa procedures and also have a nice walk or dinner in the surrounding of the nature. And we also have many sanatoriums where a tourist can enjoy his trip to the fullest. Some places with good weather for leisure are called "Shakhimar-dan", "Chartak", "Zaamin", "Tibet", Chimgan and Char-vak. Zaamin sanatorium is known as "Uzbek Switzerland" because it has lots of tall old trees that give off a nice smell. The air is already good up high in

the mountains, so it's a good place to get better. The Aktash Sanatorium is a famous vacation spot in the mountains with pretty views of forests and rivers called Aktash and Ayubsai. The country's favorite place to go skiing is called "Amirsoy". It's really big, about 900 hectares! It was built to match ski resorts around the world. It's on the north side of Maigashkan Mountain in the Tien Shan mountains, specifically the Beldersay area in Bostanlyk (Aytmetova, 2021).

Figure 3: Shakhimar-dan, Uzbekistan *Figure 4: Amirsoy ski resorts, Uzbekistan*

Source: KUN.UZ, 2015

Source: Atera.Uz, 2023

In the figures 3 and 4 nature-made destination (Shakhimar-dan) and the most known place for winter travel (Amirsoy) are shown. It is very great that we have such kind of places but the tourist experience should not be limited only within the visiting beautiful places of the nature and doing only some activities. Regarding "Amirsoy" tourists can still do winter sports and extreme activities. But what about summer season? Again, the example of South Korea will show a great solution. There is a place called Yeosu which is surrounded by the sea. They created rail bike there. It is pity that there are no big seas in Uzbekistan but we have a plenty of rivers where such kind of activities as riding a bike could be also provided.

Figure 5: Yeosu Ocean Railbike

Source: Korea Tourism Organization, 2023

There are many other places with the proximity to the nature in South Korea as well except Yeosu (Figure 5). For example, Jeju-do province, Bukhasan National Park of Seoul which amuse with their beauty and breathtaking views of the nature. Just by walking in those places a person can do even pilgrimage. By the way, pilgrimage does not stand for only religious purposes but more for the physical and psychological experiences. Because while walking on foot a person can achieve the self-awareness and be in one harmony with the nature (a bit similar to “yoga”). So, if we create some pilgrimage routes in Uzbekistan’s nature-made destinations tourists can definitely enjoy anti-stress activity by just walking.

Conclusion. The South Korea has shown perfect results in developing the wellness tourism. Especially by creating the “Haliu” (Korean wave), spa centers and anti-stress cafes. Along with them South Korea has increased the popularity of the rural tourism as well. In some aspects, this country and Uzbekistan have many similarities regarding the rural tourism mostly. However, it would be great to take some examples from South Korea to enhance the popularity of the wellness tourism in Uzbekistan too. There are a lot of recreational and healthcare spots in Uzbekistan but there is a lack of exactly stress revealing activities and touristic offers in the sphere of the wellness tourism. By

travelling more to the nature made destinations a person can also get rid of the stress, meaningly that it would help to his wellbeing. And people should not always choose the same destinations and get the same service. They should be ready to the new spots, especially those places which are connected with the wellness tourism. So, try to travel, explore and enjoy more during your journey in Uzbekistan!

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